

Stochastic multi-criteria decision analysis description_ALIGNED_V2

Excel file

- **Fine-tuning the Excel file (all sheets):**
 - have been made cleaner and clearer,
 - Increased the understanding and readability by using different colors and the sustainability-specific indicators, see below.
 - Adjusted from very general indicators (e.g. indicator X) to more sustainability-specific indicators (e.g. GHG (greenhouse gas emissions) for each pillar of sustainability to make it more tangible and understandable and less theoretical for the sustainability audience.
 - The product number has been increased from three to four products (product A, B, C, and D).
- **Sheet: Input parameters and results:**
 - Added another field for the uncertainty levels (sigma) to better distinguish between the mean and the sigma values.
 - Added a **weighting scheme** that allows the user to adjust the weighting of indicators based on their preference.
 - Note that the sheet '**weights (w)**' has been linked to the weighting scheme, adjusting the model to the chosen weightings.
 - Improved the ranking diagram and added 4 diagrams to show the probability of rankings among different products.
 - This improves the understanding of the results and makes the user aware of the probabilities of ranks.
 - The interpretation and result field has been adapted to the new version.
- **Sheet: weights (w):**
 - Has been adapted from random weights to chosen weights that are defined in the **Sheet: Input parameters and results**.

Description:

The description of the Excel file has been adapted to the new Excel file version and its more sustainability-specific indicators.

Techno-economic assessment description_V2

Excel file

The Excel file remains as it is. There are no changes made.

Description:

The description remains as it is. Only a few corrections on grammar, spelling, punctuation, and format have been performed.

Quantification model for social indicators description_ALIGNED_V2

Excel file

The Excel file model and structure remain as it is. Only a few data points have been updated to the year 2025 for the fair wage potential indicator.

Description:

The description remains as it is. Only a few corrections on grammar, spelling, punctuation, and format have been performed.